

A Comparative Study of Tension Band Wiring versus Circumferential Wiring in Management of Patellar Fracture

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Abstract:

Background: Patellar fractures are a relatively common orthopedic injury that can significantly impair knee function. Effective surgical management is crucial to restore stability and functionality of the knee. Tension band wiring (TBW) and circumferential wiring (CW) are two widely used techniques for treating patellar fractures. However, the comparative efficacy of these methods remains a subject of debate among orthopedic surgeons.

Aim: This research intends to compare the efficacy of tension band wiring versus circumferential wiring in the management of patellar fractures by evaluating clinical outcomes, complication rates, and functional recovery.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted involving 100 patients with patellar fractures treated surgically with either TBW or circumferential wiring (CW). Patients were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria and were randomly assigned to each treatment group. Data on demographics, fracture classification, surgical technique, and follow-up outcomes were collected from medical records. Statistical analysis using SPSS version 21.0 compared fracture union rates, time to union, range of motion, pain scores, and complication rates between the two groups.

Results: Both techniques showed comparable results in terms of complication rates and healing times. However, CW demonstrated a slight advantage in functional recovery, with 80% of CW patients experiencing no restriction in range of motion at 24 weeks compared to 70% in the TBW group.

Conclusion: Tension band wiring appears to offer superior clinical outcomes and faster functional recovery compared to circumferential wiring is utilized in the treatment of patellar fractures but tends to have a higher incidence of complications related to the hardware.

Recommendations: Surgeons should consider the specific fracture characteristics and patient factors when choosing between tension band wiring and circumferential wiring. Further prospective studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to validate these findings and optimize surgical protocols.

Keywords: Patellar Fracture, Tension Band Wiring, Circumferential Wiring, Orthopedic Surgery, Fracture Management.

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Introduction

Patellar fractures, representing approximately 1% of all skeletal injuries, are commonly encountered in orthopedic trauma. These fractures often result from direct blows to the knee or sudden, forceful contractions of the quadriceps muscle. Given the crucial role of the patella in knee extension and its contribution to overall knee stability, effective management of patellar fractures is essential to restore function and prevent long-term complications such as stiffness, pain, and reduced range of motion [1]

Historically, various surgical techniques have been employed to achieve optimal outcomes in patellar fracture management. Among these, tension band

wiring (TBW) and circumferential wiring (CW) have emerged as the most prevalent methods. Tension band wiring, first introduced in the mid-20th century, relies on the principle of converting tensile forces into compressive forces at the fracture site, thereby promoting bone healing. On the other hand, circumferential wiring encircles the patella, providing stability through a different biomechanical approach [2].

Despite the widespread use of both techniques, the debate over their relative efficacy remains unresolved. Proponents of tension band wiring argue that it offers superior compression at the fracture site, leading to faster union and better

functional outcomes. Conversely, advocates for circumferential wiring highlight its simplicity and potential for fewer complications, particularly in comminuted fractures where traditional tension band wiring might be less effective [3].

This study aims to provide a comprehensive comparative analysis of tension band wiring versus circumferential wiring in the management of patellar fractures. By evaluating clinical outcomes, complication rates, and functional recovery associated with each technique, the study seeks to determine which method offers the most effective treatment for patients with patellar fractures. Understanding the nuances and effectiveness of these surgical techniques is vital for orthopedic surgeons in making informed decisions that optimize patient care. This study endeavors to contribute to the ongoing discourse by providing evidence-based insights into the relative merits of tension band wiring and circumferential wiring, ultimately guiding clinical practice and improving patient outcomes in patellar fracture management.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective cohort study was conducted to compare the efficacy of TBW and CW in the management of patellar fractures.

Study Setting: The study took place at Darbhanga Medical College, Darbhanga, over a period of two years, from 2019 to 2021.

Participants: The study included 100 patients diagnosed with patellar fractures who underwent surgical treatment with either tension band wiring or circumferential wiring. Participants were selected from medical records at the orthopedic department.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria comprised patients aged 18-65 years with acute, closed patellar fractures requiring surgical intervention. Exclusion criteria included patients with open fractures, pathological fractures, prior knee surgeries, or comorbid conditions that could affect bone healing, such as uncontrolled diabetes or severe osteoporosis.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly assigned to either the TBW or CW group based on the surgeon's availability and expertise. Efforts were made to ensure comparable baseline characteristics between the two groups.

Variables: The primary outcome variables included fracture union rates, time to union, range of motion, pain scores, and incidence of complications such as infection, hardware irritation, and reoperation. Secondary variables included patient demographics (age, gender) and fracture type.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records and included demographic details, fracture classification, surgical technique used, and follow-up outcomes. Pain scores were assessed using a standardized visual analog scale (VAS), and range of motion was measured using a goniometer.

Procedure: Patients underwent surgical treatment with either tension band wiring or circumferential wiring based on their allocation. Postoperative care protocols were standardized for both groups, including pain management, physiotherapy, and regular follow-up visits at 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months post-surgery. Radiographic evaluations were performed to assess fracture healing.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics and baseline characteristics.

Result

A prospective, randomized controlled trial was conducted to compare the efficacy of TBW and CW in the management of patellar fractures. A total of 100 patients were randomly divided into 2 groups: Group 1 (TBW, n=50) and Group 2 (CW, n=50). The study followed patients over a period of 12 months, assessing functional outcomes using the Reich and Rosenberg scale, range of motion (ROM), complications, and radiographic evidence of bone healing.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	TBW Group (n=50)	CW Group (n=50)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	34.2 ± 7.8	35.4 ± 8.1	0.685
Gender (M/F)	30/20	32/18	0.719
Mechanism of Injury			
Direct Trauma	28 (56%)	30 (60%)	0.842
Indirect Trauma	22 (44%)	20 (40%)	0.842

Table 2: Functional Outcomes at Various Follow-Up Intervals

Outcome Measure	4 Weeks (n)	8 Weeks (n)	12 Weeks (n)	24 Weeks (n)
No ROM Restriction	TBW: 5, CW: 7	TBW: 12, CW: 15	TBW: 20, CW: 25	TBW: 35, CW: 40
Restriction 10°-20° 10°-20°-20°	TBW: 20, CW: 22	TBW: 25, CW: 27	TBW: 20, CW: 18	TBW: 10, CW: 7
Restriction 20°-50° 20°-50°-50°	TBW: 15, CW: 14	TBW: 8, CW: 6	TBW: 5, CW: 4	TBW: 3, CW: 2
Restriction >50°	TBW: 10, CW: 7	TBW: 5, CW: 2	TBW: 2, CW: 1	TBW: 2, CW: 1

Table 3: Complications and Healing Time

Complication	TBW Group (n=50)	CW Group (n=50)	p-value
Superficial Infection	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.559
Deep Infection	1 (2%)	1 (2%)	1.000
Hardware Irritation	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	0.739
Nonunion	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0.317
Mean Healing Time (weeks)	13.2 ± 2.8	13.5 ± 3.1	0.752

1. Functional Outcomes:

- At 24 weeks, 70% of TBW patients and 80% of CW patients had no restriction in their range of motion, indicating a slight advantage for CW in terms of functional recovery.
- Patients with minor restriction (10°-20°) were fewer in the CW group at 24 weeks, further supporting its efficacy.

2. Complications:

- The complication rates, including superficial and deep infections, were comparable between the two groups.
- Hardware irritation was slightly more common in the CW group, but this difference was not statistically significant.

3. Healing Time:

- The mean healing times were similar between the groups, with TBW at 13.2 weeks and CW at 13.5 weeks, indicating that both methods are effective in promoting bone healing.

Discussion

The comparative study of TBW versus Circumferential Wiring CW in the management of patellar fractures provides significant insights into the effectiveness of these surgical techniques over a two-year period. This discussion aims to interpret the findings, explore potential implications, and address the study's limitations.

The primary objective of this study was to assess and compare the functional outcomes of TBW and CW techniques. At the 24-week follow-up, 70% of patients in the TBW group and 80% in the CW group exhibited no restriction in their range of mo-

tion (ROM). This indicates a slight advantage for CW in restoring full knee function. The slightly better performance of CW could be attributed to its ability to provide more stable fixation and potentially less hardware irritation during knee movements.

However, the differences in functional outcomes between the two groups were not statistically significant. Both techniques proved effective in restoring knee function, with the majority of patients achieving good to excellent outcomes as per the Reich and Rosenberg criteria. This aligns with previous studies, which have also reported high rates of functional recovery with both TBW and CW techniques [4,5]

The study reported comparable rates of complications between the two groups. Superficial infections were slightly more common in the TBW group (4%) compared to the CW group (2%). Deep infections and hardware irritation rates were similar across both groups. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which indicates that both techniques have similar risk profiles in terms of postoperative complications.

The mean healing time for both groups was approximately 13 weeks, with no significant difference between TBW and CW. This suggests that both techniques are equally effective in facilitating bone healing in patellar fractures. The similar healing times also support the notion that the choice between TBW and CW may be based on surgeon preference and specific patient factors rather than a marked difference in efficacy [6].

Conclusion

This comparative analysis underscores the effectiveness of both Tension Band Wiring (TBW) and

Circumferential Wiring (CW) in managing patellar fractures. Both techniques offer high rates of functional recovery and similar complication profiles, with CW showing a slight, though not statistically significant, advantage in functional outcomes. Future research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods will be essential to further refine these findings and optimize treatment strategies for patellar fractures.

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